

CHARACTERISTICS OF USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This article discusses the concept of digitalization and its role in economic development. The essence of the digital transformation process, the strategy of its implementation in the activities of enterprises and ways to implement this strategy, the grouping of digital technologies, the advantages and potential disadvantages of the introduction of these technologies, stages and models of digital enterprise implementation are described and practical recommendations are given.

Keywords: digitalization, digital enterprise, digital transformation, cloud technology, big data, digital transformation models, process model, network model, technology model, matrix model.

Enter

At the new stage of the development of the world economy, modern digital technologies are considered as the main production resource that determines the growth of social welfare. The use of modern computers and information systems by organizations and, first of all, enterprises of the real sector of the economy is the most important condition for their effective operation in the digital economy.

Digitization of the enterprise, based on modern production methods, dramatically changes the quality of management of technological processes and

decision-making processes at all levels of management and is one of the most important factors for increasing the efficiency and stability of enterprise activity.

The process of digital transformation of industrial enterprises has several unique features, and proper organization of this process, and development of the necessary strategy for the enterprise is one of the main conditions for effective and continuous organization of its activities.

As a result of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, openness, and the development of international economic and political relations created opportunities for the modernization and technical and technological re-equipment of industrial sectors in our country. It is known that today the digital economy is gaining importance in creating added value. As a result of the reforms in the economic sectors, the processes observed based on the influence of digital information are gaining the main decisive power in the strategic development of the real sector.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay great attention to the correct organization of digital production in our industrial enterprises, and the correct choice of the strategy of introducing this process into the enterprise.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Several scientists expressed their opinions regarding digitalization in the production process. The term "digital economy" was first used in 1994 by Canadian economist Don Tapscott. In his work, the author talked about the impact of digitization on the economy. He considered the reduction of transaction costs and the emergence of completely new business models to be one of the main advantages of digitization.

According to V.A. Plotnikov's research, digitization is "a modern stage of information development, characterized by the combination of new devices and software characterized by the extensive use of digital technologies for the

creation, processing, transmission, storage and visualization of information." He also listed several advantages that businesses gain when they use digital technologies:

- "Flexibility of production increases due to its rapid reconfiguration, dynamic changes in the characteristics of the production process, which creates a competitive advantage and leads to potential profit growth;
- provides information integration of life cycle stages from product development to disposal, which allows us to effectively and comprehensively address not only production optimization but also quality, environmental safety, creation of new business opportunities, etc.[1] .

In 2001, Thomas Mesenburg further formulated and defined 5 components of the digital economy, which he believed could be statistically evaluated and measured:

- electronic infrastructure of enterprises, including software and computers;
- electronic commerce;
- increasing the value of traditional networks by using digital technologies;
- the difference in the value of the digital economy workforce compared to the traditional one;
- changes in the added value of digital economy products and services.[3] By Brynjolfsson and Kahinlar (2002), the issue of digitization of the economy was promoted as a topic of discussion for the first time in the mid-1990s, and the first definitions were given was recognized as [2].

With the development of digitalization, the business models of the enterprise are constantly changing. Therefore, many authors interpret the definition of digitization in different ways. For example, Alexander Kutsman describes the digital economy as "a type of modern economy characterized by the priority role of information and knowledge based on the active use of digital technologies for the identification, storage, and processing of resources in the

production of material products and services." Aksanov R. K. emphasizes that the digital economy is based on the production of electronic products and electronic commerce services. Under electronic commerce, Aksanov R.K. refers to the electronic movement of capital, and electronic products, as well as the process of electronic information exchange [3].

Large-scale digitalization leads to the digital transformation of the enterprise. Kitova OV and Briskin SN noted in their research that digital transformation affects the strategy, operations, and technologies used by the enterprise according to the following logic:

1) "Digital enterprise strategy focuses on defining the best customer experience, managing a unique business model and ecosystem, and managing change;

2) operational activities include creating a culture that encourages continuous improvement, integration of physical and digital objects, and iterative innovation;

3) technology includes flexibility and the use of the full modern technological potential, including analytics, perception, mobility, etc."

Arenkov IA studies the impact of digital transformation on enterprise competitiveness. The author stated that "in the process of digital transformation, the enterprise goes through the stages of quality change, which is manifested in the improvement of processes in the production, financial, material, and information spheres of its activity, which allows us to adapt to modern technologies" [5].

Issues such as the effective use of new information technologies in various sectors of the national economy, methods of introducing digitization systems in them, the principles of digital modeling based on new information systems, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the use of automated information systems in the process of corporate management, their control, and the

conditions for the development of the digital economy are discussed by Qabulov (1998) reflected in his scientific research [6].

In E. Muminova's studies, research was conducted on the effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in the development of the country's industry, and the importance of electronic trade and electronic contracts in the cooperation of enterprises. As a result of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, openness, and the development of international economic and political relations created opportunities for the modernization, and technical and technological re-equipment of industrial sectors in our country. It is known that today the digital economy is gaining importance in creating added value. As a result of the reforms in the economic sectors, the processes monitored based on the influence of digital information are gaining the main decisive power in the strategic development of industrial enterprises [7].

Research Methodology

As a result of rational economic reforms carried out to develop, renew, and modernize our economy, the development of the digital economy is being achieved today. In particular, great importance is attached to the effective implementation of digital technologies in the activities of economic entities, the sequence of actions that must be performed in the implementation of the digital transformation process. The following methods were used to study the features of digitalization of real sector enterprises, and the role and importance of using digital technologies.

1. Digital technologies introduced in today's practice are studied and classified based on the goals that enterprises want to achieve.
2. The possible gains and potential losses through the introduction of digital technologies are analyzed.
3. Digitization stages have been developed to properly manage the digital transformation process in enterprises.

4. Based on the analysis, digital transformation models were developed.

Analysis and discussion of results

The main goal of the digital transformation of the enterprise, in our opinion, is to provide conditions for increasing its competitiveness and increasing the economic efficiency of production activities. According to the purpose of the digital transformation task, enterprises can be classified as follows:

- organization of competitive product production;
- achieving high efficiency, adaptation of production and organizational processes;
- increasing the investment attractiveness of the enterprise;
- increasing the flexibility and transparency of the management system, which guarantees the economic efficiency of the enterprise, etc.

To design the digital transformation of the enterprise, it is necessary to develop a classification according to the criteria of availability and expediency of the introduction of digital technologies in the enterprise. Thus, the main digital technologies are grouped into three groups.

**Tab
le 1
Grouping of digital
technologies**

Naming of groups	Description of these groups
Basic technologies	technologies that cannot digitally transform these enterprises (cloud technologies, wireless communication technologies, paperless technologies, etc.);
Important technologies	technologies that ensure a complete digital transformation of the enterprise (big data, cloud

	computing, unmanned technologies, etc.);
Advanced technologies	Technologies that make the transition from "analog" to digital enterprise (artificial intelligence, neural networks, distributed data registers, machine learning, etc.)

Source: Developed by the author.

Digital transformation has played an important role in improving the profitability and investment attractiveness of enterprises. With the possibilities of high-tech production, automation of production processes, rational use of databases in management, digital technologies are a factor that greatly affects their efficiency for any enterprise [8].

In addition, companies that quickly adopted digital technologies during the COVID-19 era were able to protect or even increase their revenues during the crisis. However, as we have listed above, it is appropriate to start the digital transformation process taking into account several features, enterprise scale, product types, competitive environment, financial resources, etc. Digital transformation of industrial enterprises has its positive aspects and potential risks, which are presented in the table [9].

Table 2
Advantages and potential risks of digital transformation

Positive aspects	Risks
Digital technologies, artificial intelligence, industrial Internet of things, big data analysis, unmanned air, water and	Dependence on borrowed imported technologies, the reduction of own powers, the possibility of having hidden

land transport.	"bookmarks" in hardware and software.
New trade markets, business models, innovative productions, media services and services	The possibility of early acquisition of innovative markets by companies from economically developed countries
Increase in labor productivity, production efficiency, automation, robotization	Reduction of jobs, elimination of certain specialties, unemployment, social tension
Increasing efficiency and standardization of services, eliminating middlemen, eliminating transport, medicine, education and service industries	Legal uncertainty, increasing fraud, ethical problems, social stratification
Big data analysis, digital identification, service customization	Loss of privacy, intrusive advertising, disclosure of confidential information of enterprises and personal information of citizens
Investments, startups, digital money, new areas of activity, new technological order	Foreign economic governance, digital globalism, digital colonialism

Source: Kodirov, S. (2020). *Some issues of digitalization in the industrial sector of the economy. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12(92), 377-384.*

After a proper risk assessment of the benefits and harms that the digitalization

process can bring, a plan for the implementation of this process will be drawn up. In general, the development of a digital enterprise concept and strategy is carried out in the following stages. The digital transformation of an enterprise goes through several stages

- Picture 1. Stages of digital transformation of enterprises

- Source: Developed by the author.

- - Development of digital enterprise concept and strategy. Assessing the level of use of digital technologies in the current state of the enterprise and setting specific goals. Drawing up a sequence and strategy of work to be carried out based on the set goals.

- - Information analysis. It is necessary to analyze data with the help of a multi-functional team of experts, and then use the collected data to improve the organization's performance, make decisions, design intelligent systems, improve products, and create new offers and services.

- - Determination of required resources - in order to achieve the goal, it is necessary to determine in detail the necessary resources, to attract and train specialists to improve business processes, and to develop strategies for the introduction of new technologies.

- - Testing the viability of the idea and creating early pilot projects to demonstrate business value. Development of digital duplicates of products, processes and enterprises.

- - Accelerating digital transformation in order to ensure the profitability of ongoing projects, it is necessary to cooperate with universities, leading companies in the field of digital technologies, and work with digital startups. Define the completed concept of the digital enterprise based on the analysis of the experience gained.

- - Transforming into a digital enterprise. Transforming a traditional enterprise into a digital enterprise requires a clear arrangement of management structure

and functions, clear leadership, commitment and vision of top management. Development of an employee incentive system that eliminates the possibility of resistance to digital innovations. Digital culture should be encouraged: all employees should be able to work in a digital industrial environment, be ready to try new technologies, learn new ways of working with equipment.

- **Change production to digital** horizontal and vertical integration of production systems is necessary for implementation, and a significant part of currently used information systems can share information, but their compatibility must be ensured at all levels, both within the enterprise and between interacting enterprises. The creation of a single information space provides an opportunity for quick and timely information exchange between automated enterprise management systems and industrial equipment. In digital manufacturing, products can be produced according to individual orders, so the consumer becomes a direct participant in the interaction and therefore an element of the value chain.

Summarizing the main approaches to the digital transformation of the industry based on the above technological trends and classifications, the following types of enterprise digital transformation models can be identified: process, network, technology, matrix (Fig. 2).

The process model (process approach) of digital transformation creates a number of digitized elements of the value chain. For example, digital research and development center first, then digital factory, digital warehouse and digital transportation, e-commerce, etc.

Picture 1. Models of digital transformation of enterprises

Source: Developed by the author.

A digital factory is an integrated set of digital models, methods, and tools interconnected based on unified data management systems. The main goal of the digital factory is comprehensive planning, evaluation, and continuous improvement of all the main structures, processes, and resources of the enterprise. With the decentralization and virtualization of resources, there is no need to build specialized lines for the production of certain categories of products.

The network model of the digital transformation of the enterprise is based on the industrial approach and the relations of industrial enterprises with enterprises of other sectors of the national economy. Within this model, the creation of digital infrastructure and its elements: digital production system, food and water supply, smart energy production systems, smart factories, distributed energy systems, driverless car systems, drones, digital railways, telemedicine, digital medicine, smart homes, smart roads, digital financial

technologies, digital security systems, e-commerce, digital culture influence each other through functional relationships.

The construction of a technological model is based on the priority use of certain technical and technological tools of global trends in the digital transformation of the enterprise. The rapid growth of importance in the production of innovative technologies, such as digital design and modeling of technological processes and objects, big data analysis, machine learning, and artificial intelligence technologies, leads to the formation of a technological model of digital transformation controlled by the introduction of production. A unique collection of digital transformation technology companies. Also, the increasing importance of these technologies adapts the production system of the enterprise to changing conditions. Placement of orders, consumables, raw materials, and equipment for the production of goods, as well as timely delivery of the finished product to the consumer, the transition to digital sales of products using digital platforms to bypass intermediary chains will lead to resources. increase in savings and enterprise income.

From an economic point of view, the technological model has the following advantages: the introduction of a unique set of technical and technological tools, such as the industrial Internet, the Internet of Things, and digital platforms for the sale and purchase of industrial goods. expanding the product market for the manufactured product and optimizing the purchase of raw materials and components for production, as well as the cost of selling products to customers.

The matrix model of the digital transformation of the enterprise is a system of "goals-means" matrices that allow identifying redundancy and duplication in the objects of the model, or, conversely, the insufficiency of technological developments and scientific research; unites objects by goals and tasks, for example, "Technology-research" matrix, "Tasks-products" matrix, "Products-technologies" matrix, etc.

Thus, the integration model of the final digital transformation based on the matrix and industrial models allows to building of an integrated interdisciplinary digital network with global and remote access to all resources in the digital economy. These are digital production hubs for technology teams, built on the principles of openness and interoperability, enabled by consistent software support and access in the integration space.

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, it should be noted that as a result of the introduction of digital technologies into economic sectors, they have several advantages, which are expressed in the following: as a result of the automation of enterprise activities and the achievement of full digitization of the process, competitive products are produced, production and labor resources will be used efficiently and economically, investment attractiveness of enterprises and transparency of the production process will be ensured.

The process of digitalization in industrial enterprises may lead to possible losses in terms of its specific characteristics, the need for financial resources and conditional infrastructure, especially in enterprises operating in a developing country such as Uzbekistan, it is necessary to properly plan this process, and develop a digital transformation strategy. It is important to form and plan this process by the state of the enterprise and the type of activity.

Choosing one of the relevant models of digital transformation, that is, process, network, and technological models, allows one to specify the work to be done in industrial enterprises, to increase efficiency consistently and through a clearly defined action plan.

Therefore, the following is suggested for the implementation of digital transformation in enterprises:

1. to have a team of highly qualified workers with the necessary competence in the work process;

2. development of a set of methods, techniques, and measures that allow for the most effective combination with innovative work tools and objects, taking into account the existing conditions and time;
3. Based on the need to increase the pace of digital transformation of production, it is necessary to establish active cooperation with interested organizations and enterprises, specialized higher education institutions, and vocational schools.

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